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TEACHING PROBLEM SOLVING TO ENGINEERS IN THE ERA OF BIG DATA AND INDUSTRY 4.0

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Industry 4.0 promises a fourth industrial revolution to better manage the way value is produced. One enabler of I4.0 is Big Data Analytics, which is often embraced as a panacea. In fact, the complexity of processing higher volume, more frequent, more diverse and more messy data makes things worse for engineers aiming to build, deploy and maintain processes to drive a ‘smart factory’. Engineers in industry are often swamped and ill-equipped to handle these challenges, particularly when the application domain is growing fast.

One problem with Big Data Analytics (especially in teaching!) is that it often bypasses the methods and best practices of statistical thinking developed and proven over many decades. In many one-shot studies, machine learning algorithms are applied looking for highest prediction accuracy, sometimes without due regard for the pedigree of the data used. Furthermore, most data scientists are neither interested in learning more about the process or system under study nor in validating their findings with subject matter experts. In contrast, an engineer does not just want to predict future defect rates, but also to develop a long-term strategy to understand root causes and reduce defects further through process improvement.

During the workshop participants will see live demonstrations of a holistic approach to Big Data Analytics, which reflect some essential elements of Statistical Engineering. Key concepts covered include:

- Design of Experiments and data quality (to address the pedigree of the data)
- Visualization to explore data and models (“You can see a lot just by looking”)
- Advanced analytics (beyond machine learning methods)

Our holistic approach helps to showcase how statistical thinking works with Engineering to drive process understanding and innovation. The demonstrations will feature JMP Pro, which offers the most complete support for real-world applications of Industry 4.0. No prior familiarity with JMP is required. All workshop content will be shared with participants.